



Fig. S1. nuDNA ML tree inferred with IQ-TREE from 150 nuclear gene loci. The smaller figure in the upper left corner shows the branch lengths. The values before each node indicate Maximum Likelihood Bootstrap (MLBS) from IQ-TREE.